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DIGITAL INDIA PROGRAMME AND IMPACT OF DIGITALISATION ON INDIAN MARKET AND ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

We are living in arena of technologies and digital world. The digital world is a world where the best possible use is made of digital technologies. The ‘Digital India’ programme, an origination of honorable Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi, targets to make government services available to people digitally and enjoy the benefit of the newest information and technological innovations. It is a programme to prepare India for a knowledge future. The motive behind the concept is to connect rural areas with high speed internet network and improving digital literacy. Digital technologies which include cloud computing and mobile applications transpire as the catalysts for shaping our world.

The Digital India programme faces the serious barriers in implementation. This research is an effort to overcome these barriers and to find some remedies for providing better future to everyone. The motto of this research is to find out how the government services can be available to every citizen electronically and improve the quality of life of every citizen.

Key Words: Digital India, Digital Technology, e-Kranti, e-Governance

INTRODUCTION:

Today, we can't imagine our life without technology. In the twenty-first century, one of the most important technologies is the power of the digitization. The system, which allows individuals to communicate globally. Digital India is a programme to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. It was launched on **2 July 2015** to ensure that government services are made available to citizens electronically by improving online infrastructure and by increasing internet connectivity or by making the country Digitally empowered in the field of technology.

It consists of three core components as follows:

- The creation of digital infrastructure.
- Delivering services digitally.
- Digital literacy

Digital India is an umbrella programme which covers many departments. This initiative will ensure that are government services and information are available anywhere, anytime on any device that are user friendly and secured with Digital India project, the government is ready for the big programme by connecting every service with e-power.

VISION

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I. Digital infrastructure as a utility to every citizen: - This vision provides high speed internet as a core utility public services like the land records, certificates and many more will be made available online or public cloud. It gives a safe and secure cyber space in the country.

II. Governance and services on demand: - Under this vision, every government services or information is available in real time from online & mobile platforms. It makes financial transactions electronics & cashless and provides single window access to every individual.

III. Digital empowerment of citizens: - All digital resources will be available universally in Indian languages. All documents and certificates to be available on the cloud.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To know how the technologies and connectivity will come together to make an impact on all aspects of governance and improve the quality of life of citizens.

2. To find out how the government services can work effectively with practical solutions and innovative ideas to accomplish the vision of a digital India-a reality
- 3.To study the impact of digital India programme on the upliftment of Indian rural economy.
4. To study how Digital India programme will lead to empowerment of rural entrepreneurship in the country.

SCOPE OF DIGITAL INDIA:

The scope of overall programme is –

- The digital India is a great plan to develop India for a knowledge future.
- On being transformation– to realize IT (Indian Talent) +IT (Information Technology) =IT (India Tomorrow).
- The programme pulls together many schemes like e-Health, e-Sign, e-Education etc.
- It weaves together a large number of ideas and thoughts into a single, comprehensive goal so that each of them is seen as part of a larger goal.
- Each individual element stands on its own. But is also a part of the largest picture.
- The common branding of program as Digital India highlights their transformative impact.

DIGITAL INDIA:

The programme contains tasks that target to make sure that govt. services are available to people digitally and people get advantage of the newest information and connections technological innovation. Gandhiji felt that 'India resides in its villages,' and technology will help the villages to grow and prosper. Digital libraries, online magazines, e-books can be made available for free which will further help in knowledge sharing. PM Modi rightly said in his speech in San Jose, "I see technology as a means to empower and as a tool that bridges the distance between hope and opportunity. Social media is reducing social barriers. It connects people on the strength of human values, not identities." Technology is a bridge indeed, a bridge that connects the hope that India's villages will be educated and aware to the opportunity of internet and access to information from across the world. 'Digital India' is not just an initiative but a need for this country, where majority of population still does not have access to the world of internet. The Digital India initiative seeks to lay emphasis on e-governance and transform India into a digitally empowered society. It is to ensure that government services are available to citizens electronically. Digital India also aims to transform ease of doing business in the country. The Department of Electronics and Information Technology (deitY) anticipates that this program will have a huge impact on the Ministry of Communication and IT. The program is projected at Rs 1, 13,000 crore which will prepare the country for knowledge-based transformation. It will focus on providing high speed internet services to its citizens and make services available in real time for both online and mobile platform. Modi's government is focussing on providing broadband services in all villages of the

country, tele-medicine and mobile healthcare services and making the governance more participative.

How digital India will be realized: Pillars of digital India

Digital India programme is an all-inclusive programme of government of India that covers various ministries and departments of the government. The programme has to be implemented with mutual co-ordination and cooperation among these departments and ministries with the help of Department of Electronics and Information Technology.

Pillars of Digital India

1. Broadband highways –

- Broadband for all rural
- Broadband for all urban.
- Mandate communication infrastructure in new urban development and buildings.

2. Universal access to mobile connectivity –

- Increasing networking services.
- To connect unconnected areas by using technologies.
- To provide universal phone connection.

3. Public internet access programme -The government aims to provide internet services to 2.5 lakh villages which comprises of one in every panchayat by March 2017 and 1.5 lakh post offices in the next two years. These post offices will become Multi-Service centres for the people.

4. E-governance - The government aims to improve processes and delivery of services through e-Governance with UIDAI, payment gateway, EDI and mobile platforms. School certificates, voter ID cards will be provided online. This aims for a faster examination of data.

5. E-kranti –

- Technology for Education e-education.
- Technology for Health e-healthcare.
- Technology for Farmers.
- Technology for Security.
- Technology for Justice.
- Technology for Financial inclusion.

6. Information for all – Information must be available for everyone through electronic means or network based resources. Regular interactions of government with citizens are essential through social media sites or web based programmes, for good e-governance.

7. Electronics manufacturing – Electronic equipment's are the basic requirement for the programme to be implemented successfully. Manufacturing indigenous technology is important to attract investment in the sector and to reduce imports. Improving their prospects in securing a good job in today's digitally changing environment.

8. Early harvest programmes – These programmes are those which run with a deadline with in which they have to be completed. The timespan for these programmes consist of a short time period, i.e., within 3 years. Some of the projects included in it are biometric attendance, wi-fi in all universities, secure e-mail within government, school books to be e-books, National portal for lost and found children, etc.

The digital India programme focuses on timely, i.e., 3 years, completion of most of its projects, specifically the projects under information for all and early harvest programmes. The programme aims at restructuring, remodelling, revising and refocussing of existing schemes to enhance their effectiveness for implementation.

Projects under Digital India Programme-

Under digital India programme the Government of India has undertaken some projects. These projects are as follows:

- (a) Digital locker system of the digital India programme will help citizens to digitally store their important documents like pan card, passport, mark sheets and degree certificates. It will help to minimize the usage of physical documents and will provide secure access to Government issued documents.
- (b) Another key project under Digital India programme is My gov.in which has been implemented as a platform for citizen engagement in governance, through a “Discuss, Do and Disseminate” approach.
- (c) Swachh Bharat Mission Mobile App is one of the projects of Digital India programme which will help the people and the government organization for achieving the goal of Swachh Bharat Mission.
- (d) E- Sign framework would allow citizens to digitally sign a document online using Aadhar Authentication.
- (e) Online registration system under the e- Hospital application has been introduced. This application provides important services such as online registration, payment of fees and appointment, online diagnostic reports, enquiring availability of blood online etc.
- (f) National scholarship portal which will put an end to elongated scholarship process.
- (g) The Government of India has undertaken an initiative namely Bharat Net, a high speed digital highway to connect all 2.5 lakh gram panchayats of the country. This would be the world's largest rural broadband connectivity project using optical fibre.
- (h) BSNL has introduced Next Generation Network, to replace 30 years old exchanges, which is an IP based technology to manage all types of services like voice, data, multimedia/video and other types of packet switched communication services.

Key drivers of growth in the IT sector

- Low cost of operation and tax advantages
- Supportive government policies
- Availability of technically skilled manpower
- Rapid introduction of IT technologies in major sectors such as telecom, BFSI.
- Strong growth in export demand
- use of new technologies like cloud computing
- Government established SEZs

Demonetization and Digital Banking Environment in India and its Effect on Customer Satisfaction in India:

In terms of impact, few events can equal the demonetization of high-value Indian currency notes which took effect from November 9, 2016. The stories and rumors have been prolific, arguments and counterarguments endless; queues have reappeared in the age of 4G and the internet, and the media frenzy has been unparalleled. Economists appear to be widely divided over the efficacy and the impact of the move on the black money, which is variously estimated at 23 percent to 75 percent of the GDP. Demonetization is intended to flush out the black money and encourage a move to a cashless (or less cash-based) state and bring the parallel sector into the mainstream economy.

Critics argue that these motives have little economic justification and are more political in nature, in view of the coming state assembly elections in Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. To them, the amount of counterfeit currency in circulation is too small to be of any significance (0.004 percent of total cash in circulation); critics also point out that demonetization is unlikely to bring out much black money, since the bulk of it is held in illiquid assets such as land or gold and jewelry. Meanwhile, the common man has had to bear the economic hardship as 90 percent of all transactions are paid in cash. The brunt of the impact falls on those associated with the informal sector, which accounts for 80 percent of all jobs, where 85 percent of the workers are paid in cash.

Impact of Demonetization:

- 1) Black Money and Corruption:**By demonetization, Black money will be taken out of Indian system. As predicted by ICICI Securities Primary Dealership the government's plan to remove INR 500 and INR 1,000 notes from circulation will disclose up to INR 4.6 lakh crore in black money. Corruption will also be automatically reduced by removing black money from economy.

Arithmetic of Demonetization of High- Denomination

Notes in circulation (value in INR billion)	7854	6326	14180
Notes with banks together with other govt. agencies @ 30%	2356	1898	4254
Notes with public @70%	5498	4428	9926
Conversion by public for new notes with old (%)	60	40	-
Total value of converted by public (INR billion)	3299	1771	5070
Scenario 1: Total value not converted by public @50%(INR billion)	2199	2657	4856
Scenario 2: Total value not covered by public @50% of 20% of black money(INR billion)			4520
Scenario 3: Replicating 1978, with 25% not coming back	1374	1107	2482

Source: SBI Research, RBI

The table depicts the public holding of high denomination notes worth Rs. 9926 billion as on march 2016. There are 3 scenario in table. In scenario 1 and 2 it is assumed that 50% of the notes of higher denomination do not return to the system. It is also reasonable to expect that 60% of Rs. 500 notes and 40% of Rs. 1000 notes would be exchanged at banks/ post offices and RBI before March 31, 2017. Based on such estimates, roughly round Rs. 4.5 lakh crore of money could disappear from the system.

2) Funding:

Funding for smuggling and terrorism will take a blow since all the money will get back to bank and from there it is easy to identify the fake currency. Demonetization thus affects the funding of terror networks in Jammu and Kashmir, North-eastern states and the other areas.

3) Real estate:

Another impact of the demonetization would be reduction in cash transactions in real estate. This is likely to reduce to real estate prices and make it affordable. In the short term, prices of real estate would come down for the same reason above. There will be fewer suitcases moving.

4) Elections:

Demonetization has shocked political parties. Many states like Punjab and Uttar Pradesh, cash donations are a huge part of "election management". Political parties will find themselves helpless as cash hoards are often undeclared money. So upcoming elections 2017 will be transparent to the some extent.

5) Gold/Silver and Jewellery:

After demonetization the demand for gold and other precious metals rise greatly. Because people are trying to invest their black money in gold to make it white in short period. But demand for gems and jewellery to decline in the next two to three quarters.

6) Digital payments:

People adopting online payments system such as Paytm etc. after ban for high denomination currency in India. Digital transaction systems, E wallets and apps, online transactions using E banking, usage of Plastic money (Debit and Credit Cards), etc. will definitely see substantial increases in demand. This behavioral change could be a game changer for India in the near future.

7) Fake Currency:

The impact on the fake currency would be more significant. Many dealers with the existing counterfeit notes would be trapped as they would have to take the notes to the bank and have better chances of getting their racket exposed. Thus, they have only option to destroy their notes and incur losses.

8) GDP:

The sudden decline in money supply and increase in bank deposits is going to adversely impact consumption demand in the economy in the short term. This, coupled with the adverse impact on real estate and informal sectors may lead to lowering of GDP growth.

9) Markets:

There will be positive move in markets in long run that could bring confidence of overseas investors in Indian stock markets. Market goes a bit down in the short and medium term. India is still a very attractive destination on a long-term basis. It is not the best market in the next three months.

10) Decease in Interest Rates:

We will see lowering interest rates for education loans, home loans and medical loans very soon. It will make higher education and medical facilities more accessible. This change is hard to undo because if any subsequent government increases loan it will suffer huge backlash.

11) Lower Inflation:

As the black money goes out of the system the money supply will shrink to some degree. This will reduce inflation rate in the absence of any open market interventions by the Reserve Bank of India.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF IMPACT ON INDIAN STOCK MARKET AND ASIAN STOCK MARKET IN PRESENT SCENARIO:

At the time of writing, the Indian markets have fallen a bit more than other emerging markets in Asia. The S&P BSE Sensex is down 3.8%, which is more than more or less all other Asian emerging markets. The possibility of a Donald Trump win is keeping markets on the edge worldwide. The extra fall in the Indian markets compared to others could be due to many factors, including high valuations, but it's very likely that the demonetization effect is mainly responsible for the fall.

That is clearly seen if we dig a little deeper. The Sensex is made up of very large companies which may not be impacted as much by the demonetization process. BSE's mid-cap and small cap indices have fallen by over 6% each at the time of writing. And in truth, the largest impact of the government's move will be in the unorganized sector, which isn't represented in the markets.

The below true picture is reflected in sectoral indices such as the BSE Realty index, which is down as much as 15% at the time of writing. Some stocks such as DLF Ltd are down nearly 20%. This industry is known to entertain cash transactions of large magnitude. Similarly, stocks of jewellery companies such as Titan Industries Ltd have fallen by around 11% as well, perhaps because a lot of gold purchases are through cash. Besides, stocks of mid- and small-sized finance companies which collect payments in cash have fallen by 8-10%.

Information technology stocks, for now, are down around 3%, which is more or less in line with the broad markets. While these companies will be unaffected by the demonetization process, this reflects a concern about a Trump presidency and a possibility of anti-outsourcing measures.

THE EXPERIENCES FROM SOME COUNTRIES:

Russia:

On its last legs, the country under Mikhail Gorbachev in January 1991 withdrew large-ruble bills from circulation in a move to take on the black economy. The reform failed to halt inflation, and instead served mainly to accelerate a slide in public confidence in the government. As political infighting combined with economic collapse, Gorbachev faced a coup attempt that August which destroyed his authority and led to the Soviet break-up the following year. Learning lessons, Russia's 1998 redenomination of the ruble, when it removed three zeroes, went altogether more smoothly.

North Korea:

In 2010, the regime of then-dictator Kim Jong-Il mounted a reform that knocked off two zeros from the face value of the old currency in an effort to tighten control of the economy and close

black markets. Combined with a poor harvest, the measure left the country with severe food shortages, according to reports at the time. Surging rice prices stoked unrest that prompted an unusual apology from Kim, and -- reports suggested -- the execution of the ruling party's head of finance.

Zaire:

Dictator Mobutu Sese Seko faced increasing economic disruptions in the early 1990s, when his administration mounted successive banknote reforms. A plan to withdraw obsolescent currency from the system in 1993 saw a surge in inflation and a collapse in the exchange rate against the dollar. After a civil war, Mobutu was ousted in 1997

Myanmar:

In 1987, the country's military junta invalidated as much as 80 per cent of the value of money in circulation, according to reports at the time -- as in other such initiatives, it was directed at curbing the black market. One result was the first student demonstrations in years. Deepening economic unease helped trigger mass protests across the nation the following year that led to a government crackdown that killed thousands of people.

Ghana:

The country in 1982 got rid of its 50 cedi note to crack down on tax evasion, address corruption and mop up excess liquidity. The move eroded confidence in the banking system as people turned to foreign currency or physical assets instead. The black market for currency flourished.

As rural dwellers had to walk miles to the nearest banks to exchange their money, and after the deadline passed, there were accounts of bundles of notes abandoned as worthless.

Nigeria:

In 1984, the military government led by Muhammadu Buhari instituted an anti-corruption crackdown that involved issuing new banknotes with a different color, forcing the replacement

of old ones within a limited period. The move was one of a series that failed to fix a debt-burdened and inflation-ridden economy. Buhari, who is now in power again, was eventually ousted in a coup the following year.

(i) 3.3 CONCLUSION:

The demonetisation undertaken by the government is a large shock to the economy. The impact of the shock in the medium term is a function of how much of the currency will be replaced at the end of the replacement process and the extent to which currency in circulation is extinguished. While it has been argued that the cash that would be extinguished would be “black money” and hence, should be rightfully extinguished to set right the perverse incentive structure in the economy, this argument is based on impressions rather than on facts. While the facts are not available to anybody, it would be foolhardy to argue that this is the only possibility. As argued above, it is possible that these cash balances were used as a medium of exchange. In other words, while the cash was mediating in legitimate economic activity, if this currency is extinguished there would be a contraction of economic.

In an e-world where, business is done at the speed of thought, the real challenge for the future lies in anticipating the demands of the new age and providing sustainable solutions. CRM strategy must cover all the market segments such as retail customers, Indian corporate sector, trade and agricultural sector for their banking requirements. The banks must adopt e-CRM ‘Customer-centric’ focus approach, as it is believed that products should be devised for the customers and not the other way around.

Banks must build their brand image in assuring customers about the safety of their money and security of transaction on the Net. Moreover, CRM based alone on Internet will seem to be a wrong strategy for banks in India. Jose Fonellosa of Spain BBVA, which acquired first e-CRM, says internet is at best a zero sum game for banks. For high end products, customer cannot only rely on e-banking. For social interactions, people would like to visit their traditional brick and mortar branches.

Thus Customer Relationship Management is essential to compete effectively in today's marketplace.

So far, it can be said that this is a historical step by the Modi Govt. and should be supported by all. This decision of govt. will definitely fetch results in the long term. From an equity market perspective, this move would be positive for sectors like Banking and Infrastructure in the medium to long term. This could be negative for sectors like Consumer Durables, Luxury items, Gems and Jewellery, Real Estate and allied sectors, in the near to medium term. This move can lead to improved tax compliance, better fiscal balance, lower inflation, lower corruption, complete elimination of fake currency and another stepping stone for sustained economic growth in the longer term.

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